

Research

Modelling of Substance-Abuse and Its Progression Stages

Kalabu Salisu Ahmad^{*}, Usamatu Usman², Abdul Audu Ibrahim³ & Ibrahim Yusuf Inuwa⁴
^{*,2,3,4}*Department of Mathematics and Statistics, Federal Polytechnic Bauchi, Bauchi state, Nigeria*

**Corresponding author*

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Abstract: *Substance-abuse mathematical model is proposed to study the dynamism of substance-abuse and its various stages of progression from the justification that substance abuse leads to substance addiction with the development of tolerance and dependence. We analyze the model where we prove existence and uniqueness of the solution to the system, positivity of the solution, invariant region of the solution, substance-free equilibrium state of the system and discuss local stability as well as global stability of the model at substance-free stability state. Epidemiological approach is adopted in proposing the mathematical model which enables scientists to study the dynamism of substance-abuse and its various stages of progression.*

Keywords: *Mathematical model, equilibrium point, basic reproduction number and model stability.*

Introduction

Substance-abuse is at times called drug-abuse. In 1956, World Health Organization (WHO) and American Psychological Association (APA) considered drug-abuse as a disease which is defined by the illicit consumption of any naturally occurring or pharmaceutical substance for the purpose of changing the way, in which a person feels, thinks, or behaves without understanding or taking into consideration the damaging physical and mental side-effects that are caused [7]. The use of drug to cure an illness, prevent a disease or improve health is termed drug use. But when a drug is taken for reasons other than medical, in an amount, strength, frequency or manner that causes damage to the physical or mental functioning of an individual, it becomes drug-abuse [9].

[4] proposed a model which described heroin use within a fixed community where they considered individuals as divided into Susceptible, Drug Users and Drug Users Undergoing

Treatment. They showed the existence of a stable state equilibrium and suggested both a situation where heroin use will be eradicated and one where it will remain an endemic.

[5] proposed a heuristic control theory model that describes smoking under restricted and unrestricted access to cigarettes. The model was based on the allostasis theory and uses a formal representation of a multi-scale opponent process. The model stimulates smoking behavior of an individual and produces both short-term and long term smoking patterns. By introducing a formal representation of withdrawal and craving-like processes, the model produces gradual increases over time in withdrawal and craving-like signals associated with abstinence and shows that after three (3) months of abstinence, craving disappears. The model was programmed as a computer application allowing users to select simulation scenarios. The application links images of brain regions that are activated during the binge/intoxication, withdrawal, or craving with corresponding simulated states. The model was calibrated to represent smoking patterns described in peer-reviewed literature; however, it is generic enough to be adapted to other drugs, including cocaine and opioids. Although the model does not mechanistically describe specific neurobiological processes, it can be useful in prevention and treatment practices as an illustration of drug-using behaviors and expected dynamics of withdrawal and craving during abstinence.

[3] proposed a model to reflect the spread of drug use in population and enumerated the role of dynamic modeling in drug-abuse epidemiology. The researcher stated that dynamic models can be used to generate estimates where data are sparse or to verify hypotheses or predict trends by means of “what if” scenario analyses. He also enumerated that the models that can be used effectively in the drug field are essentially models of epidemics that describe the spread of a disease in a population in order to provide evidence for public health-oriented interventions and policies.

[8] proposed a six-typology compartment model of trends in the use of illicit drugs in Italy. A deterministic linear ODE framework, where parameters were estimated using Italian data was obtained and analyzed. The system showed an evolution toward a steady state. The model represented a theoretical development in drug policy analysis, as it shows the relevance of flux parameters, which were in principle subject to modifications.

[14] presented a new mathematical modeling framework to investigate the effects of illicit drug use in community. The transmission process in the model was captured as a social “contact” process between the susceptible individuals and illicit drug users. Epidemic and endemic

analysis were conducted with a focus on the threshold dynamics characterized by the basic reproduction number. Illustrative numerical results were presented with a case study in Cape Town, Gauteng, Mpumalanga and Durban communities of South Africa. The model was extended to incorporate time dependent intervention strategies.

[13] considered a compartmental model of substance users in the two forms of rehabilitation. A periodic function was used to illustrate fluctuations of drug users entering rehabilitation. Two basic reproduction numbers $\mathfrak{R}_0$ and $[\mathfrak{R}_0]$ where $\mathfrak{R}_0$ is for model with fluctuations and $[\mathfrak{R}_0]$ for the model without. The model was analyzed in terms of the two reproduction numbers. The model was fitted to data on the two forms of rehabilitations and projections made. The main results showed that the disease goes to extinction if the threshold value $\mathfrak{R}_0$ is less than unity, whilst the disease persists if the threshold value is larger than unity. Also, there exists a positive solution when the threshold is above unity.

Many scientific efforts are being put in place to study drug-abuse dynamics in society considering some societal factors and effects but yet scientists fail to consider and model how the menace of drug-abuse develop from its root stage to development of tolerance and dependence; hence the lacuna this research work satisfies.

The model formulation

The model is formulated under the following assumptions that, total population comprises Susceptible (S), Substance Abusers (A), Substance Addicts (Q), substance Tolerants (T), substance Dependents (D) and Rehabilitants (R); new recruitment into the system is in the susceptible class, rehabilitation does not provide permanent recovery therefore rehabilitated persons could become susceptible again and the rehabilitation center is strictly inpatient so as to avoid relapsing.

The model equations are:

$$\frac{dS}{dt} = \mu + \gamma R - \left(\frac{\beta_1 A}{N} + \alpha \right) S \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{dA}{dt} = \frac{\beta_1 SA}{N} - (\delta_1 + \beta_2 + \alpha + \rho_1) A \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{dQ}{dt} = \beta_2 A - (\delta_2 + \beta_3 + \alpha + \rho_2) Q \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{dT}{dt} = \beta_3 Q - (\delta_3 + \beta_4 + \alpha + \rho_3) T \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{dD}{dt} = \beta_4 T - (\delta_4 + \alpha + \rho_4) D \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{dR}{dt} = \delta_1 A + \delta_2 Q + \delta_3 T + \delta_4 D - (\gamma + \alpha + \rho_5) R \quad (6)$$

$$\text{where } N = S + A + Q + T + D + R \quad (7)$$

subject to initial conditions,

$$t = 0, S(0) = S_0, A(0) = A_0, Q(0) = Q_0, T(0) = T_0, D(0) = D_0, R(0) = R_0 \quad (8)$$

Existence and uniqueness of the model solution

Lemma 1: If f_i and $\frac{\partial f_i}{\partial y_i}$ are continuous functions of x, y in some interval rectangle;

$\{(x, y) : a < x < b; c < y < d\}$ containing the point (x_0, y_0) , in some interval $x_0 - d < x < x_0 + d$ such that $d > 0$, then there exist a unique solution [2].

Theorem 1: Both f_i and $\frac{\partial f_i}{\partial y_i}$ exist and are continuous.

Proof: From (1) to (6), let

$$f_1 = \mu + \gamma R - \left(\frac{\beta_1 A}{N} + \alpha \right) S$$

$$f_2 = \frac{\beta_1 SA}{N} - (\delta_1 + \beta_2 + \alpha + \rho_1) A$$

$$f_3 = \beta_2 A - (\delta_2 + \beta_3 + \alpha + \rho_2) Q$$

$$f_4 = \beta_3 Q - (\delta_3 + \beta_4 + \alpha + \rho_3) T$$

$$f_5 = \beta_4 T - (\delta_4 + \alpha + \rho_4) D$$

$$f_6 = \delta_1 A + \delta_2 Q + \delta_3 T + \delta_4 D - (\gamma + \alpha + \rho_5) R$$

It is clear that $f_i; i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 6$ are continuous, hence the system has an existing solution.

Partial derivative of the functions with respect to the dependent variables are given as:

$$\frac{\partial f_1}{\partial S} = -\left(\frac{\beta_1 A}{N} + \alpha\right)$$

$$\frac{\partial f_2}{\partial A} = \frac{\beta_1 S}{N} - (\delta_1 + \beta_2 + \alpha + \rho_1)$$

$$\frac{\partial f_3}{\partial Q} = -(\delta_2 + \beta_3 + \alpha + \rho_2)$$

$$\frac{\partial f_4}{\partial T} = -(\delta_3 + \beta_4 + \alpha + \rho_3)$$

$$\frac{\partial f_5}{\partial D} = -(\delta_4 + \alpha + \rho_4)$$

$$\frac{\partial f_6}{\partial R} = -(\gamma + \alpha + \rho_5)$$

Since both f_i and $\frac{\partial f_i}{\partial y_i}$ are continuous, then the system has an existing and unique solution.

Positivity of the model solution

Lemma 2: Let the initial conditions be $\{(S_H, S_V)(0) > 0, (I_M, L_R, I_R, L_{MR}, I_{MR}, I_V)(0) > 0\} \in \psi$. Then the solution set $\{(S_H, I_M, L_R, I_R, L_{MR}, I_{MR}, S_V, I_V)(t)\}$ is positive $\forall t > 0$ [10].

Theorem 2: Let the initial solution set $\{(S, A, Q, T, D, R)(0) > 0\} \in \mathfrak{R}_+^6$ then the solution set $\{(S, A, Q, T, D, R)(t)\}$ for the model equations (1) to (6) is positive $\forall t > 0$.

Proof: From (1), since $\frac{dS}{dt} = \mu + \gamma R - \left(\frac{\beta_1 A}{N} + \alpha\right) S$ to prove the positivity we consider

$$\frac{dS}{dt} \geq -\left(\frac{\beta_1 A}{N} + \alpha\right) S$$

Separating the variables we have,

$$\frac{dS}{S} \geq -\left(\frac{\beta_1 A}{N} + \alpha\right) dt$$

Integrating we have,

$$\int \frac{dS}{S} \geq -\int \left(\frac{\beta_1 A}{N} + \alpha\right) dt$$

From which we have,

$$\ln S \geq -\int \left(\frac{\beta_1 A}{N} + \alpha\right) dt + C_1$$

Taking exponents on both sides we have,

$$S \geq e^{-\int \left(\frac{\beta_1 A}{N} + \alpha\right) dt + C_1}$$

Since S , A and N are time dependent then we have,

$$S(t) \geq u_1 e^{-\int \left(\frac{\beta_1 A(t)}{N(t)} + \alpha\right) dt} \tag{9}$$

where $u_1 = e^{C_1}$, a constant.

From (8), the initial conditions, substituting $t = 0$ and $S(0) = S_0$ into (9) we have,

$$S_0 \geq u_1 \tag{10}$$

Substituting (10) into (9) we have,

$$S(t) \geq S_0 e^{-\int \left(\frac{\beta_1}{N(t)} + \alpha\right) dt} > 0 \tag{11}$$

From (2), since

$$\frac{dA}{dt} = \frac{\beta_1 AS}{N} - (\delta_1 + \beta_2 + \alpha + \rho_1) A$$

$$\frac{dA}{dt} \geq -(\delta_1 + \beta_2 + \alpha + \rho_1) A$$

$$\frac{dA}{A} \geq -(\delta_1 + \beta_2 + \alpha + \rho_1) dt$$

$$\int \frac{dA}{A} \geq -\int (\delta_1 + \beta_2 + \alpha + \rho_1) dt$$

$$\ln A \geq -(\delta_1 + \beta_2 + \alpha + \rho_1)t + C_2$$

$$A \geq e^{-(\delta_1 + \beta_2 + \alpha + \rho_1)t + C_2}$$

$$A(t) \geq u_2 e^{-(\delta_1 + \beta_2 + \alpha + \rho_1)t} \tag{12}$$

where $u_2 = e^{C_2}$, a constant.

From (8), the initial conditions, substituting $t = 0$ and $A(0) = A_0$ into (12) we have,

$$A_0 \geq u_2 \tag{13}$$

Substituting (13) into (12) we have,

$$A(t) \geq A_0 e^{-(\delta_1 + \beta_2 + \alpha + \rho_1)t} > 0$$

From (3), since $\frac{dQ}{dt} = \beta_2 A - (\delta_2 + \beta_3 + \alpha + \rho_2)Q$, then

$$\frac{dQ}{dt} \geq -(\delta_2 + \beta_3 + \alpha + \rho_2)Q$$

$$\frac{dQ}{Q} \geq -(\delta_2 + \beta_3 + \alpha + \rho_2)dt$$

Integrating,

$$\ln Q \geq -(\delta_2 + \beta_3 + \alpha + \rho_2)t + C_3$$

$$Q(t) \geq e^{-(\delta_2 + \beta_3 + \alpha + \rho_2)t} e^{C_3}$$

$$Q(t) \geq u_3 e^{-(\delta_2 + \beta_3 + \alpha + \rho_2)t} \tag{14}$$

Where $u_3 = e^{C_3}$

From (8), the initial conditions, substituting $t = 0$ and $Q(0) = Q_0$ into (14) we have,

$$Q_0 \geq u_3 \tag{15}$$

Substituting (15) into (14) we have,

$$Q(t) \geq Q_0 e^{-(\delta_2 + \beta_3 + \alpha + \rho_2)t} > 0$$

From (4), since $\frac{dT}{dt} = \beta_3 Q - (\delta_3 + \beta_4 + \alpha + \rho_3)T$

$$\frac{dT}{dt} \geq -(\delta_3 + \beta_4 + \alpha + \rho_3)T$$

$$\frac{dT}{T} \geq -(\delta_3 + \beta_4 + \alpha + \rho_3)dt$$

Integrating,

$$\ln T \geq -(\delta_3 + \beta_4 + \alpha + \rho_3)t + C_4$$

$$T(t) \geq e^{-(\delta_3 + \beta_4 + \alpha + \rho_3)t} e^{C_4}$$

$$T(t) \geq u_4 e^{-(\delta_3 + \beta_4 + \alpha + \rho_3)t} \tag{16}$$

Where $u_4 = e^{C_4}$

From (8), the initial conditions, substituting $t = 0$ and $T(0) = T_0$ into (16) we have,

$$T_0 \geq u_4 \tag{17}$$

Substituting (17) into (16) we have,

$$T(t) \geq T_0 e^{-(\delta_3 + \beta_4 + \alpha + \rho_3)t} > 0$$

From (5), since $\frac{dD}{dt} = \beta_4 T - (\delta_4 + \alpha + \rho_4)D$

$$\frac{dD}{dt} \geq -(\delta_4 + \alpha + \rho_4)D$$

$$\frac{dD}{D} \geq -(\delta_4 + \alpha + \rho_4)dt$$

Integrating,

$$\ln D \geq -(\delta_4 + \alpha + \rho_4)t + C_5$$

$$D(t) \geq e^{-(\delta_4 + \alpha + \rho_4)t} e^{C_5}$$

$$D(t) \geq u_5 e^{-(\delta_4 + \alpha + \rho_4)t} \tag{18}$$

Where $u_5 = e^{C_5}$

From (8), the initial conditions, substituting $t = 0$ and $D(0) = D_0$ into (18) we have,

$$D_0 \geq u_5 \tag{19}$$

Substituting (19) into (18) we have,

$$D(t) \geq D_0 e^{-(\delta_4 + \alpha + \rho_4)t} > 0$$

From (6), since $\frac{dR}{dt} = \delta_1 A + \delta_2 Q + \delta_3 T + \delta_4 D - (\gamma + \alpha + \rho_5) R$

$$\frac{dR}{dt} \geq -(\gamma + \alpha + \rho_5) R$$

$$\frac{dR}{R} \geq -(\gamma + \alpha + \rho_5) dt$$

Integrating,

$$\ln R \geq -(\gamma + \alpha + \rho_5)t + C_6$$

$$R(t) \geq e^{-(\gamma + \alpha + \rho_5)t} e^{C_6}$$

$$R(t) \geq u_6 e^{-(\gamma + \alpha + \rho_5)t} \tag{20}$$

Where $u_6 = e^{C_6}$

From (8), the initial conditions, substituting $t = 0$ and $R(0) = R_0$ into (20) we have,

$$R_0 \geq u_6 \tag{21}$$

Substituting (21) into (20) we have,

$$R(t) \geq R_0 e^{-(\gamma + \alpha + \rho_5)t} > 0$$

It shows that the solution set $\{(S, A, Q, T, D, R)(t)\}$ is positive for all time t .

Invariant region of the model solution

Lemma 3: Let A be a deterministic model that describes human population, say $N(t)$, whose state variables and parameters are assumed to be non-negative and that there is no disease induced death. Let $S_i(t)$ and $I_i(t)$ denote the finite number of compartments for susceptible and infected individuals respectively at a given time t for $i = 1, 2, 3 \dots n$. Let μ and Λ denote the natural death rate and recruitment rate respectively, where $\mu > 0$ and $\Lambda > 0$. Then the system of equations that describes a model A is dissipative, that is all the solutions are uniformly bounded on $\Omega \in \mathbb{R}_+^{2n}$ [12].

Theorem 3: The solution of the system will be studied in the positive invariant region

$$\Omega = \Omega_S \subset \mathfrak{R}_+^6 \text{ with } \Omega_S = \left\{ (S, A, Q, T, D, R) \in \mathfrak{R}_+^6 : N \leq \frac{\mu}{\alpha} \right\} \text{ for all time, } t > 0.$$

Proof: From (7),

$$N = S + A + Q + T + D + R$$

differentiating,

$$\frac{dN}{dt} = \frac{dS}{dt} + \frac{dA}{dt} + \frac{dQ}{dt} + \frac{dT}{dt} + \frac{dD}{dt} + \frac{dR}{dt} \tag{22}$$

substituting (1) to (6) into (22) we have,

$$\frac{dN}{dt} = \mu - \alpha N - (\rho_1 A + \rho_2 Q + \rho_3 T + \rho_4 D + \rho_5 R) \leq \mu - \alpha N$$

therefore,

$$\frac{dN}{dt} \leq \mu - \alpha N$$

$$\frac{dN}{(\mu - \alpha N)} \leq dt$$

integrating,

$$N \leq \frac{\mu}{\alpha} - \frac{e^{-\alpha(t+C)}}{\alpha}$$

taking limit as time

$$t \rightarrow \infty, N \rightarrow \frac{\mu}{\alpha}$$

Therefore

$$N \leq \frac{\mu}{\alpha} \tag{23}$$

Hence the solution of the system will be studied in the positive invariant region $\Omega = \Omega_S \subset \mathfrak{R}_+^6$

$$\text{with } \Omega_S = \left\{ (S, A, Q, T, D, R) \in \mathfrak{R}_+^6 : N \leq \frac{\mu}{\alpha} \right\} \tag{24}$$

To establish the positive invariance of Ω , the solutions of Ω remains in Ω for all time, $t > 0$.

Substance-free equilibrium point of the model

At equilibrium, $A = Q = T = D = R = \frac{dS}{dt} = \frac{dA}{dt} = \frac{dQ}{dt} = \frac{dT}{dt} = \frac{dD}{dt} = \frac{dR}{dt} = 0$ and hence

$$\text{substance-free equilibrium point, } E_0 = (S, A, Q, T, D, R) = \left(\frac{\mu}{\alpha}, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0 \right) \tag{25}$$

Basic reproduction number of the social vice

Lemma 4: Basic reproduction number can be defined as the number of new infections produced by a typical infective individual in a population at disease-free equilibrium. It can be obtained by $R_0 = \rho(FV^{-1})$ where ρ is the spectral radius or dominant eigenvalue of the next generation matrix FV^{-1} , F is the rate at which infected individuals produce new infections in susceptible compartment, and V^{-1} is the average length of time infectious individual spends in susceptible compartment during its lifetime and FV^{-1} is the expected number of new infections produced by

infected individual originally introduced into susceptible compartment where $F = \left[\frac{\partial F_i(x_0)}{\partial x_j} \right]$ and

$V = \left[\frac{\partial V_i(x_0)}{\partial x_j} \right]$ for $i \geq 1$, the number of compartments and $1 \leq j \leq m$ for the infected

compartments only. If the threshold parameter, $R_0 < 1$, then on average an infected individual

produces less than one new infected individual over the course of its infectious period, and the infection cannot grow. Conversely, if $R_0 > 1$, then each infected individual on average, produces more than one new infection, and the disease can invade the population [11].

Theorem 4: The basic reproduction number is given by $\mathfrak{R}_0 = \rho(FV^{-1}) = \max\left(\frac{\beta_1}{l_1}, 0\right) = \frac{\beta_1}{l_1}$.

Proof: From equations (2) to (5) we have, $F_i = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\beta_1 AS}{N} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$ and $V_i = \begin{bmatrix} (\delta_1 + \beta_2 + \alpha + \rho_1)A \\ (\delta_2 + \beta_3 + \alpha + \rho_2)Q \\ (\delta_3 + \beta_4 + \alpha + \rho_3)T \\ (\delta_4 + \alpha + \rho_4)D \end{bmatrix}$

where $V_i = -V_i$.

$$F = \frac{\partial F_i}{\partial x_i} = \begin{bmatrix} \beta_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$V = \frac{\partial V_i}{\partial x_i} = \begin{bmatrix} l_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & l_2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & l_3 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & l_4 \end{bmatrix}, \quad V^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{l_1} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{l_2} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{l_3} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{l_4} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$FV^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} \beta_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{l_1} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{l_2} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{l_3} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{l_4} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\beta_1}{l_1} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Using the characteristics equation $|FV^{-1} - \lambda I| = 0$, the basic reproduction number is given by:

$$\mathfrak{R}_0 = \max\left(\frac{\beta_1}{l_1}, 0\right) = \frac{\beta_1}{l_1} \tag{26}$$

If $\beta_1 < l_1$ then $\mathfrak{R}_0 < 1$ and substance abuse will die out hence the system is locally asymptotically stable subject to the initial conditions. However if $\beta_1 > l_1$ then $\mathfrak{R}_0 > 1$

where $l_1 = (\delta_1 + \beta_2 + \alpha + \rho_1)$, $l_2 = (\delta_2 + \beta_3 + \alpha + \rho_2)$, $l_3 = (\delta_3 + \beta_4 + \alpha + \rho_3)$ and $l_4 = (\delta_4 + \alpha + \rho_4)$.

Local stability of the system at substance-free equilibrium point

Lemma 5: If f , g and h are assumed to be functions of three independent variables x , y and z , obtained from a system of three equations, with an equilibrium point of the system as E , then

the Jacobian matrix of the system is given by $J = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial f}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial f}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial f}{\partial z} \\ \frac{\partial g}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial g}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial g}{\partial z} \\ \frac{\partial h}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial h}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial h}{\partial z} \end{pmatrix}$. The original system of the

equations will be stable at the equilibrium point only if the Jacobian matrix is evaluated at the equilibrium state, and all eigenvalues of $(J_E - \lambda I) = 0$ are real and negative or complex with negative real parts [6].

Theorem 5: The system is locally asymptotically stable if the inequality $\beta_1 < (\delta_1 + \beta_2 + \alpha + \rho_1)$ is satisfied (so that $a_1 < 0$).

The Jacobian matrix of the system (1) to (6) evaluated at equilibrium is given by

$$J_{E_0} = \begin{pmatrix} -\alpha & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \gamma \\ 0 & a_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \beta_2 & -a_2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \beta_3 & -a_3 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \beta_4 & -a_4 & 0 \\ 0 & \delta_1 & \delta_2 & \delta_3 & \delta_4 & -a_5 \end{pmatrix} \quad (27)$$

where $a_1 = \beta_1 - (\delta_1 + \beta_2 + \alpha + \rho_1)$, $a_2 = l_2$, $a_3 = l_3$, $a_4 = l_4$ and $a_5 = (\gamma + \alpha + \rho_5)$.

Using the characteristics equation $|J_{E_0} - \lambda I| = 0$ we have,

$$\begin{vmatrix} -(\alpha + \lambda) & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \gamma \\ 0 & (a_1 - \lambda) & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \beta_2 & -(a_2 + \lambda) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \beta_3 & -(a_3 + \lambda) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \beta_4 & -(a_4 + \lambda) & 0 \\ 0 & \delta_1 & \delta_2 & \delta_3 & \delta_4 & -(a_5 + \lambda) \end{vmatrix} = 0 \quad (28)$$

The eigenvalues are: $\lambda_i = -\alpha, a_1, -a_2, -a_3, -a_4, -a_5$, for $i = 1, 2, 3 \dots 6$. Hence the system is locally asymptotically stable if $\beta_1 < (\delta_1 + \beta_2 + \alpha + \rho_1)$ so that $a_1 < 0$.

Global stability of the system at substance-free equilibrium point

Lemma 6: We write the system as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dX}{dt} &= F(X, I) \\ \frac{dI}{dt} &= G(X, I), G(X, 0) = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (*)$$

where $X \in \mathfrak{R}^m$, denotes the number of uninfected individuals and $I \in \mathfrak{R}^n$, denotes the number of infected individuals including latent, infectious, etc, $U_0 = (x^*, 0)$, the disease-free

equilibrium point of the system, and the conditions below must be met to guarantee global asymptotic stability:

(H1). For $\frac{dX}{dt} = F(X, 0)$, x^* is globally asymptotic stable,

(H2). For $G(X, I) = AI - G(X, I)$, $G(X, I) \geq 0$ for $(X, I) \in \Omega$

where $A = D_I G(X^*, 0)$ is an M-matrix (the off diagonal elements/entries of A are nonnegative) and Ω is the region where the model makes biological sense [1].

Theorem 6: A fixed point $E_0 = (\frac{\mu}{\alpha}, 0)$ is a global asymptotic stable equilibrium point of the system ((1) to (6)).

Proof: Let the system of equations numbered (1) to (6) be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dX}{dt} &= U(X, I) \\ \frac{dI}{dt} &= G(X, I), G(X, 0) = 0, \end{aligned} \tag{29}$$

Where $X = (S, R) \in \mathfrak{R}^2$, $I = (A, Q, T, D) \in \mathfrak{R}^4$, $K(X, 0) = (\frac{\mu}{\alpha}, 0) = E_0$ and

$$H = \begin{pmatrix} \beta_1 - y_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \beta_2 & -y_2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \beta_3 & -y_3 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \beta_4 & -y_4 \end{pmatrix} \tag{30}$$

where $y_1 = (\delta_1 + \beta_2 + \alpha + \rho_1)$, $y_2 = l_2$, $y_3 = l_3$ and $y_4 = l_4$; which the off diagonal entries are nonnegative.

$$\text{Now } G(X, I) = \begin{pmatrix} G_1(X, I) \\ G_2(X, I) \\ G_3(X, I) \\ G_4(X, I) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \beta_1 A \left(1 - \frac{S}{N}\right) \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (31)$$

Since $0 \leq S \leq N$, then $G(X, I) \geq 0$.

Hence, the substance-free equilibrium state of the model is globally asymptotically stable.

Conclusion

From the outcome of the research, it has been obtained that the model is both locally and globally asymptotically stable. We prove the existence and uniqueness of the solution of the model and also state a condition for the control of the menace from the basic reproduction number obtained. We conclude that our societies are in the mess of substance-abuse due to number of individuals joining and or participating in the bad act which brings about progression into highly dangerous classes of substance abuse.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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